

Study of Effective in Ova Feeding of Folic Acid in Hatchability Traits of Broiler Chicks

Wisam Salim Al-Jumaili

Department of Animal Production, Agriculture College, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Mohammed Khalil Ibrahim Al Saeedi

College of Environmental Sciences, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Rassha Fajer Al-Jebory

Department of Medical Biotechnology, College of Science, Al-Mustaqbal University, Babylon, Iraq

Ahmed A. Al-Salhi

Department of Animal Production, College of Agriculture and Marshes, University of Dhi Qar, Iraq

Luai Saleh Khlaif Al-Khafaji

Department of Animal Production, Agriculture College, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Ali Ahmed Alaw Qotbi

Department of Animal Production, Agriculture College, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Hashim Hadi Al-Jebory

Department of Animal Production, Agriculture College, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Abstract

This study was conducted in Al-Jaflawi Poultry Company hatchery, Babylon Governorate, Iraq for the period from November 3, 2024 to November 25, 2024. 300 fertilized eggs were used, divided into five groups, each treatment containing 60 eggs, and each group had three replicates, each replicate containing 20 eggs. The experimental groups were F₁ without injection, F₂ injected with 0.25 ml of distilled water/egg, and groups F₃, F₄, and F₅ injected with 0.25% folic acid solution at a concentration of 2, 4, and 6%/egg. The study results showed a significant increase in hatchability and a decrease in embryonic mortality for the F₃, F₄, F₅ groups. The hatched chick weight of the F₅ group also increased significantly. Chick length and the weight of the remaining yolk sac increased in the chicks of F₁, F₃, F₄, F₅ groups. However, there was no significant difference between the studied groups in traits of activity traits, the percentage of abnormal chicks, and wing and leg length.

Keywords: *in ova feeding, folic acid, hatchability, broiler chicks, Physical chick's traits.*

Suggested citation: Al-Jumaili, W.S., Al Saeedi, M.K.I., Al-Jebory, R.F., Al-Salhi, A.A., Al-Khafaji, L.S.K., Qotbi, A.A.A., & Al-Jebory, H.H. (2025). Study of Effective in Ova Feeding of Folic Acid in Hatchability Traits of Broiler Chicks. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(3), 80-84. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(3).08

Introduction

The genetic improvement of rapid growth and development that accompanied broiler chickens over the past years made the nutritional needs of broiler embryos greater in order to achieve ideal growth and

reach the highest weight at hatching, as well as obtaining the highest hatching rate from fertilized eggs (Ibrahim et al., 2020; Al-Jebory et al., 2024 a,b; Alsudani et al., 2025), the hatching egg injection technology came as one of the methods used in early feeding of chicken embryos to deliver nutrients inside the egg by injection into the amniotic sac or into the air space of the egg, as the nutrients contained in the egg improve the performance of embryo growth and improve the growth performance of the subsequent hatched chicks and improve the immunity of the chicks as well as improve the histological and anatomical characteristics of the intestine, which is reflected in increasing the benefit from the feed consumed during farm rearing (AL-SAEEDI et al., 2023; Ajafar et al., 2024). Folic acid or (B9) is considered important for many metabolic processes in the fetus's body. It is important for the growth and development of the body's organs, increases the hatching rate, reduces fetal body deformities, enhances fetal immunity, increases the erythropoiesis process, and improves metabolism and the utilization of nutrients inside the egg (Abdel-Halim et al., 2021). Therefore, the current study aimed to study the effect of injecting hatching eggs on hatching traits and some physical specifications of hatched chicks.

Materials

This study was conducted in Al-Jaflawi Poultry Company hatchery/ Babylon Governorate for the period from November 3, 2024 to November 25, 2024. 300 fertilized eggs were used (60 ± 2 gm), divided into five groups, each treatment containing 60 eggs, and each group had three replicates, each replicate containing 20 eggs. The experimental groups were F₁ without injection, F₂ injected with 0.25 ml of distilled water/egg, and groups F₃, F₄, and F₅ injected with 0.25% folic acid solution at a concentration of 2, 4, and 6%/egg.

Hatching characteristics were studied according to (AL-SAEEDI et al., 2023; Ajafar et al., 2024). Physical characteristics of chicks were studied according to (Khalil ET AL., 2022). Data analysis was conducted using SAS (2012) and using Duncan (1955).

Results and Discussion

Hatch Ratio and Mortality Ratio

Table 1 shown the impact of study in hatching traits, noted significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) of all folic acid groups in hatch ratio and mortality ratio compared F₁ and F₂ groups.

Table 1. Impact of in Ova Feeding of Folic Acid in Hatch Ratio and Mortality Ratio of Broiler Chicks

Groups	Hatch ratio	Mortality Ratio
F ₁	82.00± 1.13 b	18.00±0.25 a
F ₂	82.50±0.22 b	17.50±0.30 a
F ₃	84.50±1.00 a	15.50±0.13 b
F ₄	85.75±0.13 a	14.25±1.00 b
F ₅	84.25±1.20 a	15.75±0.14 b
Sign.	*	*
„a,b values deferent at ($P \leq 0.05$)”		

Chicks Weight

The change in chick's weight at hatching shown in table (2), significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) of F_5 compared to F_2 while not significant deferent among F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4 groups.

Table 2. Impact of in Ova Feeding of Folic Acid in Chicks Weight at Hatching

Groups	Chicks weight at hatching
F_1	40.25±1.75 ab
F_2	39.62±0.62 b
F_3	40.83±2.58 ab
F_4	40.87±0.12 ab
F_5	41.11±2.11 a
Sign.	*
„a,b values deferent at ($P \leq 0.05$)”	

Chicks Hatching Traits

In table (3) noted not significant effect in abnormal chicks, wings length and leg length, at same time significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) of F_1, F_3, F_4, F_5 groups in chicks length compared to F_2 group.

There was noted not significant impact in chicks activity (table 4), significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) of F_1, F_3, F_4, F_5 groups in yolk sac diverticulum compared to F_2 group.

Table 3. Impact of in Ova Feeding of Folic Acid in Chicks Hatching Traits of Broiler Chicks

Groups	Abnormal chicks %	Chicks length (cm)	Wings length (cm)	Leg length (cm)
F_1	1.00±0.05	17.00±0.13 a	2.25±0.50	2.15±0.06
F_2	2.25±0.25	16.45±0.10 b	2.32±0.61	2.25±0.04
F_3	0.00±0.00	17.20±0.06 a	2.45±0.87	2.14±0.07
F_4	0.25±0.03	17.22±0.01 a	2.57±0.69	2.20±0.10
F_5	0.00±0.00	17.27±0.52 a	2.35±0.41	2.16±0.15
Sign.	N.S	*	N.S	N.S
„a,b values deferent at ($P \leq 0.05$), N.S: not significant”				

Table 4. Impact of in Ova Feeding of Folic Acid in Chicks Hatching Traits of Broiler Chicks

Groups	Activity (mint)	Yolk sac diverticulum (gm)
F_1	5.16±1.30	2.41±0.14 a
F_2	6.32±2.14	2.37±0.09 b
F_3	5.71±0.13	2.44±0.04 a
F_4	5.44±1.32	2.45±0.05 a
F_5	5.36±1.00	2.46±0.01 a
Sign.	N.S	*
„a,b values deferent at ($P \leq 0.05$), N.S: not significant”		

The significant improvement in hatchability, reduced mortality, and some physical characteristics of hatched chicks may be due to the effect of folic acid injections, which promote embryo growth and development by increasing DNA synthesis and rapid cell division, which enhances the growth and development of the embryos tissues and organs (Abd El-Azeem et al., 2014), it also enhances the growth and development of the fetus's skeleton and muscles through folic acid's role in mineral metabolism, particularly iron (Li et al., 2016), at the same time, folic acid plays an important role in regulating the

metabolism of proteins and fats, which increases the fetus's ability to utilize the nutrients in the egg (Liu et al., 2016), the improvement in the decrease in unsaleable chicks in folic acid injection treatments may be due to folic acid's role in reducing fetal malformations, as folic acid plays a role in reducing nervous and skeletal system malformations and reducing inflammation of the hock joint. Folic acid is also important for the formation of red and white blood cells, which increases the growth and weight of hatched chicks (Nouri et al., 2018; Abdel-Halim et al., 2021), the increased weight of the remaining yolk sac in the folic acid injection groups may be due to folic acid's role in Fat metabolism and improved energy levels in the fetus's body, which increases viability and directs excess energy to achieve better growth (Robel, 2008; Nouri et al., 2018). Researchers found that early feeding of hatching eggs improved chick hatchability and subsequent growth performance (Kadhim et al., 2021; Zaki and Al-jebory, 2021; Khalil et al., 2022; Salman et al., 2024).

Conclusion

It is concluded from the study data that injecting different concentrations of folic acid into hatching eggs improved the hatchability and some phenotypic characteristics of the chicks, and improved the level of energy utilization in the body by increasing the weight of the yolk sac.

References

- Abd El-Azeem, N. A., Abdo, M. S., Madkour, M., & El-Wardany, I. (2014). Physiological and histological responses of broiler chicks to in ovo injection with folic acid or L-carnitine during embryogenesis. *Global Veterinaria*, 13(4), 544–551. <https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.gv.2014.13.04.85231>
- Abdel-Halim, A., Mohamed, F. R., Elmenawey, M. A., & Gharib, H. B. (2021). Impact of in-ovo injection of folic acid and glucose on hatchability and post-hatching performance of broiler chickens. *World Veterinary Journal*, 10(4), 481–491. <https://dx.doi.org/10.54203/scil.2020.wvj58>
- Ajafar, M., Al-Jebory, H. H., & Al-Saeedi, M. K. I. (2024). Effect of in ova injection of lysophospholipid in hatching traits, chick's quality, and chicks physical traits of broiler (Ross 308). *Advances in Animal and Veterinary Sciences*, 12(7), 1206–1213. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17582/journal.aavs/2024/12.7.1206.1213>
- Al-Jebory, H. H., Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., Al-Jebory, R. F., Al-Jawahery, H. F. A., Ajafar, M., Abd Alzahra, I. M. A., Elsagheer, M. A., & Eletmany, M. R. (2024b). Investigating the effect of nano-metals on poultry histology: A review. *Chelonian Conservation and Biology*, 19(1), 1286–1305. [https://doi.org/10.18011/2024.01\(1\)](https://doi.org/10.18011/2024.01(1))
- Al-Jebory, H. H., Elsagheer, M. A., Qassim, A. A., Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., Al-Jebory, R. F., Qotbi, A. A. A., Ali, N. A. L., & Eletmany, M. R. (2024a). Mycotoxins and their impact on poultry health and productivity. *Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology*, 45(4), 1243–1262.
- Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., Al-Jebory, H. H., & Abood, M. H. (2022). Progress phenotypic traits of hatched chicks and growth indicators of broiler chicks fed embryonically with zinc methionine. *Archives of Razi Institute*, 77(6), 2139–2145.
- Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., Al-Jebory, H. H., & Ajafar, M. (2023). Effect of in ova injection with nano-copper in productive performance of Japanese quail exposed to pathological and environmental challenges. *Annals of Agri-Bio Research*, 28(2), 361–366.
- Alsudani, A. A., Al-Jebory, H. H., & Al-Saeedi, M. K. I. (2025). Effects of in-ovo injection of zinc-methionine on some microbial and immunological parameters of broiler. *Punjab University Journal of Zoology*, 40(1), 1–7. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17582/journal.pujz/2025/40.1.1.7>

- Duncan, D. B. (1955). Multiple range and multiple F tests. *Biometrics*, 11(1), 1–42. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3001478>
- Ibrahim, M. K., & Al-Jebory, H. H. D. (2020). Study of the effect of bee propolis on some biochemical, immunological traits and intestinal microflora of broiler chickens (Ross 308). In *1st Scientific International Virtual Agricultural Conference* (Vol. 553, p. 012022). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/553/1/012022>
- Kadhim, A. H., Al-Jebory, H. H., Ali, M. A., & Al-Khafaji, F. R. (2021). Effect of early feeding (in ovo) with nano-selenium and vitamin E on body weight and glycogen level in broiler chickens exposed to fasting condition. In *Fourth International Conference for Agricultural and Sustainability Sciences* (Vol. 910, p. 012009). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/910/1/012009>
- Li, S., Zhi, L., Liu, Y., Shen, J., Liu, L., Yao, J., & Yang, X. (2016). Effect of in ovo feeding of folic acid on the folate metabolism, immune function and epigenetic modification of immune effector molecules of broiler. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 115(3), 411–421. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114515004511>
- Liu, Y., Zhi, L., Shen, J., Li, S., Yao, J., & Yang, X. (2016). Effect of in ovo folic acid injection on hepatic IGF2 expression and embryo growth of broilers. *Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology*, 7(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40104-016-0099-3>
- Nouri, S., Ghalehkandi, J. G., Hassanpour, S., & Aghdam-Shahryar, H. (2018). Effect of in ovo feeding of folic acid on subsequent growth performance and blood constituents' levels in broilers. *International Journal of Peptide Research and Therapeutics*, 24(3), 463–470. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10989-017-9629-x>
- Robel, E. J. (2002). Assessment of dietary and egg injected d-biotin, pyridoxine and folic acid on turkey hatchability: Folic acid and poult weight. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 58(3), 305–315. <https://doi.org/10.1079/WPS20020024Cambridge University Press & Assessment>
- Salman, K. A. A., Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., & Al-Jebory, H. H. (2024). Impact of ova injection with zinc methionine on some blood parameters and glycogen level of broiler chickens exposed to feed fasting. *Advances in Animal and Veterinary Sciences*, 12(8), 1532–1538. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17582/journal.aavs/2024/12.8.1532.1538>
- Zaki, A. N., & Al-Jebory, H. H. D. (2021). Effect of early feeding with zinc-methionine on improving growth performance and some biochemical characteristics of broilers. In *1st International Virtual Conference of Environmental Sciences* (Vol. 722, p. 012035). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/722/1/012035>

